

THE MAIN TOOLS AND MECHANISMS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF STATE POLICY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS IN VILLAGES

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Abstract: The main principles of systematic development of entrepreneurship in the countryside are goal orientation, structural balance, responsibility, openness and security of resources, principles of social development.

Key words: labor resources, rural economy, labor market, diversification, organizational and legal forms of entrepreneurship, employment of rural population.

INTRODUCTION. The principle of openness envisages the participation of representatives of business entities and non-profit organizations representing their interests in the formulation and implementation of state policy in the field of entrepreneurship development, in the examination of drafts of regulatory legal documents of state and local self-government bodies. state bodies regulating the development of entrepreneurship. This principle also describes the provision of equal access to support for business entities in accordance with the terms of applicable state, regional and local support programs.

The prospect of effective development of entrepreneurship in the countryside is related to the need to create an appropriate institutional environment, introduce effective financial and investment tools for stimulating economic activity, systematically support them at the level of local self-government bodies, and coordinate the activities of business entities. all branches of government.

Using the terminology of institutional theory, it can be noted that entrepreneurial structures are also created to take advantage of opportunities that depend on the existing set of constraints. The formation of a favorable institutional environment, the emergence of new, effective institutions will help to develop entrepreneurship at a qualitatively new level, which will ensure the progressiveness of production technologies, a high level of their organization, and an increase in the quality of production. creation and development of products and services, innovative ideas.

Among the institutional factors of development of entrepreneurship in the countryside, it is necessary to highlight the most important and problematic ones in modern conditions, for example, institutions for the protection of property rights and economic freedoms. The urgency of these problems is determined by the fact that, in terms of institutional theory, business structures are created for the purpose of using useful opportunities, in addition to other purposes.

Thus, summarizing the above, it can be said that the formation of an adequate organizational and economic mechanism for the development of entrepreneurship in the village requires taking into account the systematic approach and principles of the theory of self-organization in its construction. should be aimed at implementing the basic principles of synergy as the main theory of self-organization. The basis of the organizational-economic

mechanism must be the cyclic self-supporting means of its formation, implementation and adaptation processes in a rapidly changing and unpredictable business environment. This approach takes into account the need to encourage entrepreneurs for innovative, economically efficient, socially and environmentally responsible management; supporting the processes of self-organization, self-management and self-management.

The tools and levers of the mechanism guarantee a high level of adaptability to the changing conditions of the market economy, which allows modeling the processes of rural entrepreneurship development, taking into account the non-linear interaction of external and internal factors and the influence of institutional constraints. on entrepreneurship development. The above demands the need to study the specific features of the state regulation policy on the activation of entrepreneurship in rural areas.

In our opinion, it is important to follow the classification according to the following criteria when implementing state policy measures for the formation of a network of infrastructure elements supporting small business in rural areas:

-by types of founders:

- ❖ created by employers/entrepreneurs;
- ❖ created by private individuals (citizens);
- ❖ created by state bodies;
- according to the scope of activity:
 - ❖ international, national, interregional, regional, subregional, local;
 - ❖ by forms: organizational-technical, information-analytical, financial-credit;
- by industry:
 - ❖ monoindustry; interdisciplinary; professional; clusters;

Figure 1. The main means and mechanisms of the implementation of the state policy of small business development in the countryside¹

- ❖ by focusing on a specific segment: small and medium-sized businesses; newly established business; women's business; youth business;
- ❖ according to the organizational and legal status: citizens' associations, charity structures, economic entities, economic associations, consulting structures under state structures;
- ❖ by types of activity: consulting services, audit firms, entities managing databases, investment and innovation companies, educational institutions, chambers of commerce and industry, etc.
- ❖ The above-mentioned main mechanisms and means of regulating small business potential in rural areas are presented in Figure 1.

Table 1

Peculiarities of the state policy of small business development in the countryside²

Direction of development regulation, state support and encouragement	Main features
Administrative and institutional regulation	establishment of local taxes and fees (on a preferential basis) for small business entities;
Financial and investment support	simplifying the entry of small business entities by regulating the rules for the implementation of commercial and economic activities;
Creating favorable macroeconomic environment ^a	establish an online communication system with representatives of small business entities to solve their existing problems and problems that hinder their activities
Infrastructure and resource support	promotion of the most favorable elements of business infrastructure to rural areas;
Organizational support	development of the system of training of personnel of labor professions for small entrepreneurship in the village; promoting the system of low-cost leasing services, purchasing agricultural machinery, technologies, equipment and supplies for other purposes, leasing economic activities.
Information and psychological support	development and support of the advisory system for starting and conducting business activities in rural areas;

Thus, we believe that the provision of infrastructure and resources to encourage the development of small businesses in rural areas is an important and integral direction of state

¹ Муаллиф ишланмаси

² Муаллиф ишланмаси

policy. At the same time, the formation of the small business sector in these regions requires the use of specific approaches in this area.

In particular, as a rule, promotion of the most convenient elements of business infrastructure to rural areas, development of the system of training personnel in labor professions for small businesses in the countryside, promotion of the system of cheap leasing services, purchase, sale of agricultural machinery, technologies, tools and equipment to others renting economic activities.

Their implementation is largely aimed at ensuring the high efficiency of the state policy on the development of small businesses in the countryside. At the same time, the state policy in the analyzed area will be more effective and efficient if the features of small business operation and development presented in Table 1 are taken into account and the influence is strengthened.

The importance of state support for small business in the development of regional economic complexes determines their contribution to the stimulation of entrepreneurial activity. After all, it is precisely the regions with high entrepreneurial activity that achieve the best positions in economic development. At the same time, the business environment serves as a basis for the development and stimulation of entrepreneurial activity. In this regard, it is important to study and put into practice the world experience of state support for the development of small businesses in rural areas, which is the subject of the next sub-section of the research.

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